

**POTENTIAL OF MATHO AS A LOCALIZED TEACHING STRATEGY IN ENHANCING
THE MATHEMATICAL SKILLS OF GRADE 7 LEARNERS OF GUMACA NATIONAL
HIGH SCHOOL, GUMACA WEST DISTRICT, DIVISION OF QUEZON**

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ABSTRACT

The study analyzed the performance of grade 7 learners of Gumaca National High School utilizing MATHO as a localized teaching strategy in Evaluating Algebraic Expressions, Linear Equations in One Variable, and Linear Inequality in One Variable. The results showed that outstanding learners got the highest level of improvement, followed by very satisfactory learners. Satisfactory learners ranked third in terms of progress, while fairly satisfactory learners showed some improvement. After utilizing MATHO as a localized teaching strategy, the group of very satisfactory learners achieved the highest gain score of 36.92, followed by fairly satisfactory learners who achieved 34.62. Satisfactory learners received a gain score of 33.29. The outstanding learners achieved the highest gain of 33.13, followed by satisfactory learners who achieved a commendable gain score of 31.86. The fairly satisfactory learners showed a positive advancement with a gain score of 14.57. The study found that MATHO has the potential to enhance the mathematical skills of grade 7 learners. Consistent engagement with MATHO showed significant improvement, suggesting its potential. The implementing rules and guidelines in utilizing MATHO as a localized teaching strategy to enhance the Mathematical skills of grade 7 learners are proposed.

Keywords: *Localized Teaching Strategy, Performance in Mathematics, Grade 7 Learners, Intervention Materials, Manipulative Materials, BINGO Game, MATHO Game, Potential of MATHO, Rules and Guidelines*

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics plays a crucial role in developing learners' Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) capabilities and 21st century skills. The authors also provide working definitions and reports on initial findings from a larger three-phase study aimed at exploring secondary Mathematics teachers' beliefs, attitudes, and practices towards the role Mathematics Education plays in developing learners' STEM capabilities and 21st century skills (Whitney-Smith et al., 2022).

However, recent assessments indicate a concerning trend in the performance of Filipino learners in Mathematics. According to the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) 2019 survey, Filipino learners scored significantly lower than their counterparts in other nations, with a Mathematics score of 297 – the lowest among participating countries (Magsambol, 2020). This underperformance is not an isolated incident. In the 2018 Program for International Student Assessment (PISA), which assesses 15-year-old learners across 79 countries, Filipino learners demonstrated subpar performance in both Mathematics and Science. Their scores of 353 and 357 in Mathematics and Science, respectively, fell well below the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) average of 489 for both subjects (Paris, 2019).

Addressing the challenges in Mathematics Education is crucial for the Philippines to enhance its learners' academic standing and global competitiveness. This necessitates a comprehensive approach involving educators, policy makers, and the broader community to uplift the standards of Mathematics Education in the country.

In middle school, grade 7 learners focus on developing foundational skills in Mathematics, including sets and number systems, measurement, introductory algebra, geometry, and statistics. While memory retention is crucial for long-term learning, some learners face challenges in remembering class lectures, often characterized by slow learning, weak retention, and comprehension issues (Pillado et al., 2020).

Addressing these challenges, teaching strategies play a pivotal role in creating an engaging and effective learning environment. Studies, such as the one conducted by Casinillo and Guarte (2018), emphasize the importance of teaching strategies in the learning process. Learner-centered learning, advocated by Sulaiman and Shahrill (2015), encourages active learner participation, fostering motivation and effective learning.

In the context of the Philippine Educational System, the K to 12 Enhanced Basic Education Curriculum is a dynamic framework designed to cater to the unique needs of learners. A key feature is the localization of instruction, allowing teachers to tailor

materials to their learners' specific needs. This approach, as highlighted by former Undersecretary Dina Ocampo, recognizes the importance of making the curriculum relevant by considering the unique context of each locality (Landas and Alova, 2022).

The concept of localized teaching strategies extends to instructional materials. Creus (2019) emphasizes the positive outcomes of using locally relevant materials, such as enhanced skills and creativity, increased learner performance, and improved applicability to daily life. This approach aligns with the dynamic nature of the curriculum, ensuring its effectiveness across diverse regions in the country.

The researcher, a secondary school Mathematics teacher, observed challenges at Gumaca National High School, including unmotivated learners, disengaged during math classes, bored, and doing different things instead listening in Mathematics lessons. Recognizing the need for innovation, the researcher developed the MATHO game as a localized teaching strategy. This game, a resemblance of bingo, aims to make Mathematics more enjoyable and challenging, addressing the issues of boredom and disregard of the lesson being faced by the learners. The initiative was part of a broader action research project within the Mathematics Department of Gumaca National High School, led by experienced educators with the goal of improving learners' performance, enhancing Mathematical skills, and encouraging learners to participate in Mathematics activities.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the potential of MATHO as a localized teaching strategy in enhancing the Mathematical skills of grade 7 learners of Gumaca National High School, Gumaca West District, Division of Quezon

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the performance of the learners in the summative test before and after the utilization of MATHO as a localized teaching strategy in the following least mastered competencies:
 - 1.1 Evaluating Algebraic Expression;
 - 1.2 Solving Linear Equation in One Variable; and
 - 1.3 Solving Linear Inequality in One Variable?
2. What is the gain score of the learners after exposing to MATHO as a localized teaching strategy?
3. Is MATHO, as a localized teaching strategy, has the potential to enhance the Mathematical skills of the grade 7 learners of Gumaca National High School?

4. Based on the results of the findings, what implementing rules, and guidelines in the utilization of MATHO could be proposed by the researcher?

METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

This experimental investigation took place within the Province of Quezon, situated in the CALABARZON region on Luzon Island in the Philippines. Quezon Province derives its name from Manuel L. Quezon, the first president of the Philippines to be freely elected, who hailed from Baler, a town that was once part of Tayabas, a precursor to Quezon Province. The provincial capital is Lucena, which serves as the administrative hub of this region.

The province encompasses an impressive land area measuring 8,989.39 square kilometers or 3,470.82 square miles and considered to be the longest province in the Philippine Archipelago. According to the most recent data from the 2020 Census, Quezon Province is home to a population of approximately 1.95 million residents.

Quezon Province boasts a rich tapestry of attributes that define its identity. It is renowned for its thriving agricultural sector, deeply rooted cultural heritage, spiritual significance, and an array of natural wonders, including the majestic Mount Banahaw and pristine beaches that adorn its coastline. Notably, it is distinguished by having one of the longest coastlines among the 81 provinces in the Philippines. This geographical feature underscores the pivotal role of fishing as a crucial and thriving industry, vital to the region's economy and livelihoods of its inhabitants.

Gumaca, a municipality located in the province of Quezon, is home of Gumaca National High School (GNHS). Gumaca is situated in the southeastern part of Quezon Province on the island of Luzon. It is bordered by the municipalities of Lopez to the north, Pitogo to the south, Buenavista to the west, and Lopez Bay to the east, which opens to the Philippine Sea. It has a rich historical heritage and played a role in the Philippine Revolution against Spanish colonial rule. It was a center of revolutionary activities in the late 19th century. Agriculture is a significant part of the local economy in Gumaca. The municipality is known for producing a variety of agricultural products, including rice, coconut, vegetables, and fruits. It celebrates the Pahiyas Festival, which is a colorful and vibrant event held every May. During the festival, houses are adorned with colorful agricultural products, such as rice, fruits, and vegetables, as a way of giving thanks for the harvest. The town has several historic churches, including the St. John the Baptist Parish Church, which dates back to the Spanish colonial era and is an important cultural and religious landmark in the area. It is known for its natural beauty, including scenic coastlines along Lopez Bay and nearby beaches. The municipality offers opportunities for relaxation, swimming, and beach-related activities. According to the 2020 census, it has a population of 71,942 people. It represents 3.68% of the total population of Quezon.

This research was conducted at Gumaca National High School, a public secondary school, and the mother school of Gumaca, Quezon. The school is located at Barangay Mabini, Gumaca, Quezon.

Gumaca National High School is in the “Mega School” category based on the Deped Memorandum No. 43, s. 2017 entitled 2017 Best Brigada Eskwela Implementing Schools Category. The school is composed of 201 teachers in total, 136 in Junior High School, 58 in Senior High School, 5 in ALS, and 2 in Madrasah. The school has 81 sections in total in Junior High School, 64 regular sections and 17 special programs. Grade 10 has 18 sections with 4 special programs and 14 regular sections, 22 sections in Grades 9 and Grade 8, with the same number of regular sections, 18 sections and 4 special programs, and lastly, Grade 7 has 19 sections where 14 is regular sections and 5 special programs. The special program class is composed of Special Programs in Arts (SPA), Special Program in Journalism (SPJ), Special Program in Sports (SPS), and Science Oriented Class (SOC). The learners in regular sections are heterogenous and grouped by where the learners live. The learners in the special program are homogeneous and grouped by what skills the learners have.

The selection of the research location, Gumaca National High School, was a deliberate and strategic choice made by the researcher, driven by the pressing issue about Mathematical capabilities among the learners in this school. This choice was motivated by the recognition of a significant challenge that was affecting the educational landscape: the struggle of learners in grasping fundamental Mathematical concepts.

One of the prominent issues faced by the learners in Gumaca National High School was a deficiency in their Mathematical skills. This deficiency was not merely an isolated problem but rather a complex web of interconnected factors. It was rooted in a lack of practice, an insufficient understanding of foundational Mathematical concepts, and a shortfall in overall Mathematics competencies. These factors collectively hindered the learners’ ability to excel in Mathematics.

Figure 2

The Location Map of Gumaca, Quezon

Research Population and Sample

The participants in this comprehensive study consisted of grade 7 learners enrolled in Gumaca National High School of the School Year 2022-2023, specifically representing the five sections that fall under the purview of the researcher. These sections encompassed three regular classes, namely G7-Matapat, G7-Matulungin, G7-Masunurin, and two Special Program in Sports (SPS) sections labeled as A and B. In total, the study comprised 165 learners, reflecting a diverse and representative sample of the grade 7 learners' body.

To ensure a thorough examination of the participants' academic profiles, the learners were systematically categorized based on their proficiency levels, which were determined by their previous quarterly grades. The proficiency levels included Outstanding Learners, Very Satisfactory Learners, Satisfactory Learners, and Fairly Satisfactory Learners. This stratification allowed for a nuanced analysis of the potential of MATHO as a localized teaching strategy, across varying levels of academic performance.

By incorporating learners from regular classes and those enrolled in the Special Program in Sports, the study aimed to capture a broad spectrum of learner experiences and aptitudes. The inclusion of learners with different proficiency levels ensured a comprehensive exploration of how MATHO influenced academic performance across a diverse range of learners. This approach is critical in understanding the potential impact of the teaching strategy on learners with varying learning needs and backgrounds.

The specific sections managed by the researcher were chosen intentionally to establish a more direct connection between the teaching strategy and its implementation. This targeted approach provided a unique opportunity to assess the potential of MATHO as a localized teaching strategy in a controlled and well-defined setting, ultimately contributing valuable insights to the broader educational discourse.

The participants selection process underscored the study's commitment to inclusivity and thoroughness, aiming to shed light on the nuanced relationship between the potential of MATHO as a localized teaching strategy and the academic performance of grade 7 learners of Gumaca National High School of the School Year 2022–2023.

Table 1

Respondents of the Study and their Groups According to Performance Level

Level of Performance	Number of Respondents
Outstanding	30
Very Satisfactory	46
Satisfactory	65
Fairly Satisfactory	24
Total	165

Table 1 shows the respondents of the study. The sample for this study consisted of 165 learners of the four proficiency levels: 30 outstanding learners, 46 very satisfactory learners, 65 satisfactory learners, and 24 fairly satisfactory learners.

Data Gathering Procedure

In the pursuit of addressing the Mathematical challenges haunting the learners of Gumaca National High School, the researcher embarked on a focused and systematic approach in dealing with the problem. The initial step involved in identifying a specific group of learners was the learners' previous quarterly grades, they are sorted into four categories. Outstanding Learners with grades of 90-100. Very Satisfactory Learners with

grades of 85-90. Satisfactory Learners with the grades of 80-84 and Fairly Satisfactory learners with the grades of 75-79.

Central to this practice session was the introduction of the MATHO as a localized teaching strategy. MATHO was carefully crafted to serve as an innovative resource in these instructional sessions. Its purpose was to act as a supportive and engaging aid, designed to enhance the learners' understanding of Mathematical principles and boost their Mathematical skills.

In a weeklong lesson, these dedicated learners, armed with their newfound focus and determination, delved into the practice sessions enriched by utilizing MATHO. The MATHO as a localized teaching strategy aimed not only to provide them with the opportunity to revisit and reinforce their Mathematical knowledge but also to instill a sense of confidence and competence in tackling Mathematical challenges.

Following this intensive week of educational endeavor, the learners faced another assessment: a follow-up Summative test. This test served as an essential barometer, a gauge of the potential of MATHO as a localized teaching strategy. It allowed the researcher to objectively measure any improvements in the learners' Mathematical skills, understanding, and overall performance.

The administration of this follow-up summative test marked a pivotal moment in the research. It was the point at which the potential of MATHO as a localized teaching strategy was put to the test, quantitatively. The results of this test would not only shed light on the potential efficacy of MATHO as a localized teaching strategy but also provide valuable insights into the progress and growth of the participating learners.

Research Instrument

The researcher used two instruments, the MATHO as localized teaching strategy and the summative tests.

1. MATHO

The researcher used MATHO in the lessons as a localized teaching strategy. The MATHO game is based on the BINGO game and is almost similar to it; the only difference is that in the BINGO game, the Bingo Announcer picked up a numbered ball with letter written corresponds to the number and announce that number and the letter, which determines which square gets covered on the player's BINGO card. Each letter in the word BINGO has a number that corresponds to it. Under column "B" with 5 squares, the numbers are from 1 to 15, and under letter "I" are numbered from 16 to 30, and in letters "N", "G", and "O", the numbers are from 31 to 45, 46 to 60, and 61 to 75, respectively. Each square has 15 numbers that can appear randomly with a total of 75 numbers. The BINGO game uses 1–75 natural numbers. Each square has a proportion of 15/75 or, in percentage, 20%. While in MATHO game, the MATHO Announcer or the Teacher uses a mathematical question printed in a rolled paper strip instead of a numbered ball. Each answer in each Mathematical question also has corresponding assigned letters in the

word MATHO. Under column “M” which also has 5 squares, has numbers from -5 to -1 and 1 to 5 , and under letter “A” are numbers from -10 to -6 and 6 to 10 , and in letters “T”, “H”, and “O”, has the numbers from -15 to -11 and 11 to 15 , -20 to -16 and 16 to 20 , and lastly, numbers from -25 to -21 and 21 to 25 respectively with the total of 50 numbers. MATHO card game uses integers from -25 to 25 , except 0. Each square has 10 numbers that can appear randomly and has a proportion of $10/50$ or in percentage, also has 20%. One of the lessons in the first quarter in Mathematics 7 is about operations on integers, and this is one of the first lessons in Mathematics 7 that the MATHO can be applied. The researcher made a lesson about operations on integers using MATHO.

The materials to be used: (1) MATHO Card (each learner can have 1 set of MATHO cards. Each set has 4 cards); (2) Questions are printed on a rolled paper strip; (3) Markers (can use any chips, coins, or beads); (4) Bottle shaker (or any box) where the questions are printed in a rolled paper strip is inside that bottle and will be shaken and picked by the teacher one at a time; (5) Scratch paper and pen or pencil for the learners’ solutions. The sample question is “ $y + 4$; if the value of y is -2 ”, under the least learned competency, Evaluating Algebraic Expression, the answer is 2, this answer falls under the letter M, and if the learners have that number on their MATHO cards, they can mark it.

For preparation: The teacher will choose topics in Mathematics 7 in the second quarter for which MATHO can be applied. Print the MATHO cards and the question strip. Prepare the learners and ask them to ready their MATHO cards, markers, scratch papers and pens. The mechanics of the game: (1) Set up the game; pass out one set of MATHO cards (four MATHO cards in each set) for each of the learners. Each set of MATHO cards must be unique; (2) Establish rules, explain the rules to the learners, and how someone wins the game. Rules to win; when the teacher picks up and reads off one Mathematical question at a time and allows the players to solve the problem and put their markers on one of the squares on their MATHO cards, only if the learner have the number on their MATHO cards of the answer on the question. If a learner does not have a number on their MATHO cards, the learner loses the turn; if a learner has a number on their card and that is not the solution, the player loses the round. The game continues until someone has placed straight five or four markers vertical, horizontal, and/or diagonal on the MATHO cards and or other winning patterns (See Appendix D). The first learner to mark off one of these patterns will call out the word MATHO and be the winner of the game; (3) Display the problem, the teacher would check the MATHO cards of the learner if the learner marked their cards right, if not, that learner will losses the round. (4) END of the game.

Figure 3

Sample BINGO Card

B	I	N	G	O	B	I	N	G	O
2	27	33	59	66	2	17	35	54	69
12	26	32	47	73	15	27	42	57	68
10	18	FREE 7	54	70	9	16	FREE 8	51	73
3	29	40	48	72	13	23	39	52	61
5	23	42	53	63	8	19	38	58	71

Figure 3 shows a sample of BINGO Card. The basis of the MATHO Card.

Figure 4

Sample MATHO Card

M	A	T	H	O	M	A	T	H	O
					-4	-10	14	-18	23
					-1	10	12	-17	-22
			-19	-24					
					1	7	15	17	-25
					-5	-7	11	19	-23

M	-5	-4	-3	-2	-1	1	2	3	4	5
A	-10	-9	-8	-7	-6	6	7	8	9	10
T	-15	-14	-13	-12	-11	11	12	13	14	15
H	-20	-19	-18	-17	-16	16	17	18	19	20
O	-25	-24	-23	-22	-21	21	22	23	24	25

M	-5	-4	-3	-2	-1	1	2	3	4	5
A	-10	-9	-8	-7	-6	6	7	8	9	10
T	-15	-14	-13	-12	-11	11	12	13	14	15
H	-20	-19	-18	-17	-16	16	17	18	19	20
O	-25	-24	-23	-22	-21	21	22	23	24	25

Figure 4 shows the sample MATHO cards, the one at the left is the blank MATHO card so the learners may put the numbers of their choice in each box and the table below is the distribution of numbers where the learners may choose. Each column under per

letters of MATHO has assigned numbers, and at the right side is the ready-made numbered MATHO card.

Figure 5

Sample MATHO Question Strips

MATHO Questions – Evaluating Algebraic Expressions							
Level 1 – One Variable, One Operation, One or Two Terms							
Let: $a = 1, b = 2, c = 3, x = -1, y = -2, z = -3$							
1	M	$b - 1$	1	26	H	$z + 19$	16
2	M	$y + 4$	2	27	H	$c + 14$	17
3	M	$-3x$	3	28	H	$6c$	18
4	A	$3b$	6	29	H	$z + 19$	16
5	A	$z + 10$	7	30	O	$7c$	21
6	A	$-4y$	8	31	O	$\frac{22}{a}$	22
7	T	$a + 10$	11	32	O	$b + 21$	23
8	T	$\frac{36}{c}$	12	33	O	$\frac{-72}{z}$	24
9	T	$c + 10$	13	34	O	$7c$	21

Figure 5 shows the sample MATHO Question. It will be cut into strips, rolled, and will be put in a bottle or a box. The sample question is under Evaluating Algebraic Expressions with the given values of the variables.

Figure 6

Sample MATHO Markers

Figure 6 shows sample MATHO Markers, any kind of plastics chips, coins, or beads.

2. Summative Test

These are teacher-made tests consisting of thirty multiple-choice questions covering all the three competencies that were used in the study. The first summative and second summative tests were given to learners before and after utilization of MATHO as localized teaching strategy. The Mathematics and English experts validated the three tests with comments and suggestions and guided the researcher in revising the tool. The validators were Brenda P. Libranda, HT-III, Juliet B. Ogayon MT-II (Retired), Frederick S. Brin, MT-I, Jocelyn Dapilos, T-III, Juliet Portades MT-II and all Mathematics Teachers of Gumaca National High School. They checked the alignment of test paper questions and the Table of Specifications (TOS). Mrs. Leilani T. Javier, MT-II and Mrs. Luzviminda P. Ware, MT-I of English Department checked the grammar, and test constructions.

Table 2

Results of the Validation of Utilizing MATHO as a Localized Teaching Strategy.

	Content	Format	Presentation and Organization	Accuracy and up-to-date Information	Mean
Student 1	4	4	3.8	3.8	3.90
Student 2	4	4	3.8	3.8	3.90
Student 3	4	4	3.8	3.8	3.90
Student 4	4	4	3.8	3.8	3.90
Expert 1	3.75	4	3.8	3.8	3.84
Expert 2	3.75	4	3.8	3.8	3.84
Expert 3	3.75	4	3.8	3.8	3.84
Expert 4	4	4	3.6	3.6	3.80
Expert 5	4	4	3.8	3.8	3.90
Totals	3.917	4	3.778	3.78	3.87
Verbal Interpretation: Very Satisfactory					
Legend:	4	-	Very Satisfactory		
	3	-	Satisfactory		
	2	-	Poor		
	1	-	Not Satisfactory		

Table 2 shows the result of the validation of utilizing MATHO as a localized teaching strategy. It was validated by the three Mathematics Teachers, two Master Teachers and five pilot learners of Gumaca National High School.

Statistical Treatment of the Data

The mean percentage score, and its descriptive equivalent (Based on the Curriculum and Learning Management Division-Learning Assurance for Monitoring and Progress) were used. The researcher assessed the potential of MATHO by comparing the first summative and Second Summative in learning competencies. The interpreted level of mastery from the performance is based on Curriculum and Learning Management Division - Learning Assurance for Monitoring and Progress (CLMD-LAMP) employed in Division of Quezon.

Table 3

Mean Percentage Score and its Interpreted Level of Mastery

Mean Percentage Score	Descriptive Interpretation
75.0049 % – 100 %	Highly Mastered
50.0049 % – 75 %	Mastered
25.0049 % – 50 %	Nearly Mastered
0 % – 25 %	Least Mastered

RESULTS

Part I. The Performance of the Group of Learners in the Summative Test Before and After the Utilization of MATHO as a Localized Teaching Strategy in the Least Mastered Competencies

Table 4

Summative Test Performance of the Learners in Evaluating Algebraic Expression Before and After the Utilization of MATHO as a Localized Teaching Strategy (per Learners' Category)

Level of Performance	First Summative Test Before Utilization of MATHO		Second Summative Test After Utilization of MATHO		Gain Score
	Mean Percentage Score	Descriptive Interpretation	Mean Percentage Score	Descriptive Interpretation	
Outstanding	46.08	Nearly Mastered	92.15	Highly Mastered	46.07
Very Satisfactory	45.85	Nearly Mastered	90.08	Highly Mastered	44.23
Satisfactory	45.95	Nearly Mastered	88.49	Highly Mastered	42.54
Fairly Satisfactory	38.52	Nearly Mastered	72.43	Mastered	33.91
Mean Gain					41.69
Legend:	75.0049 %	–	100 %	-	Highly Mastered
	50.0049 %	–	75 %	-	Mastered
	25.0049 %	–	50 %	-	Nearly Mastered
	0 %	–	25 %	-	Least Mastered

Table 4 presents a comprehensive analysis of the least learned competency which is Evaluating Algebraic Expressions across different levels of learners. The outstanding learners demonstrated the highest level of improvement. Very satisfactory learners closely followed, showing substantial progress. Satisfactory learners ranked third in terms of progress. Fairly satisfactory learners also exhibited some improvement. This group got the lowest gain maybe they are still exploring the game. Notably, all levels of learners demonstrated growth and moved towards mastery in Evaluating Algebraic Expressions. Before the utilization of MATHO, the level of mastery is towards mastery that indicates

this competency had not yet mastered by some of the learners but after utilization of MATHO, this competency became highly mastered. Outstanding learners showcased exceptional understanding.

MATHO served as a valuable drill for all levels of learners. The game contributed to a hands-on drill, deepening understanding, and reinforcing the application of Evaluating Algebraic Expression.

MATHO, as a game-like activity, allowed learners to view Mathematical problem-solving as enjoyable. The element of competition and enjoyment fueled active participation and a willingness to engage with the material. The overall average improvement was 41.69, indicating a positive impact on motivation and learning outcomes. The enjoyable nature of MATHO is highlighted as a factor contributing to long-term retention of Mathematical concepts. Positive associations with the learning process may lead to learners retaining information and developing a lasting interest in the subject.

This study is connected to the study of Liu et al. (2021). The study investigated the use of manipulatives in Mathematics problem-solving for high-ability learners. The authors discovered that employing manipulatives had a modest to a significant effect on high-ability learners' Mathematics problem-solving abilities. They also discovered that the effect was more substantial in cases where manipulatives were utilized in addition to traditional training rather than only an exclusive form of instruction. According to the findings, using manipulatives can assist high-ability learners in developing problem-solving skills and improving their conceptual comprehension of Mathematical ideas. Games are a somewhat effective instructional strategy for teaching Mathematics. Suggested that using games instead of traditional teaching methods led to higher learning gains. Additionally, moderator analyses were mixed in terms of statistical significance and explored effect-size heterogeneity across effects using grade level, instrument type, length of game-based intervention, country, publication type, and study year characteristics (Tokac et al., 2019). According to Talan et al. (2020), educational games typically offer higher interactivity and immersive experiences, enhancing learner engagement. Lu et al. (2022) investigates the effects of Game-Based Learning (GBL) in comparison to traditional instructional methods and suggests that Game-Based Learning interventions have a positive effect on enhancing learners' computational thinking abilities. This implies that incorporating Game-Based Learning strategies into educational settings can be an effective method for promoting computational thinking skills among learners. Overall, their study provides valuable insights into the potential benefits of utilizing Game-Based Learning in education to cultivate computational thinking.

Table 5

Summative Test Performance of the Learners in Solving Linear Equations in One Variable Before and After the Utilization of MATHO as a Localized Teaching Strategy (per Learners' Category)

Level of Performance	First Summative Test Before Utilization of MATHO		Second Summative Test After Utilization of MATHO		Gain Score
	Mean Percentage Score	Descriptive Interpretation	Mean Percentage Score	Descriptive Interpretation	
Outstanding	25.39	Nearly Mastered	58.12	Highly Mastered	32.73
Very Satisfactory	26.42	Nearly Mastered	63.34	Highly Mastered	36.92
Satisfactory	29.15	Nearly Mastered	62.44	Highly Mastered	33.29
Fairly Satisfactory	19.38	Nearly Mastered	54.00	Mastered	34.62
Mean Gain					34.39
Legend:	75.0049 %	– 100 %	-	Highly Mastered	
	50.0049 %	– 75 %	-	Mastered	
	25.0049 %	– 50 %	-	Nearly Mastered	
	0 %	– 25 %	-	Least Mastered	

Table 5 shows a comparison of the gain score achieved by learners at different levels in Solving Linear Equations in One Variable. Prior to utilization of MATHO, all levels of learners obtained an average score on the first summative test. However, after utilizing MATHO and taking the second summative test, it was observed that the group of very satisfactory learners attained the highest score with a gain score of 36.92. This was closely followed by the fairly satisfactory learners who achieved a gain score of 34.62. Meanwhile, satisfactory learners received a gain score of 33.29. Surprisingly, the outstanding group of learners showed the lowest gains in this competency. Interestingly, it can be noted that the fairly satisfactory learners performed better than the outstanding group in terms of their overall performance in Solving Linear Equations in One Variable.

It is coherent to the study of Vankúš (2021). The study investigated the influence of game-based learning in Mathematics education on learners' affective domain. This referred to the emotional and attitudinal aspects of learning, such as motivation, engagement, and enjoyment. The study likely examined how incorporating game-based learning approaches into Mathematics instruction affected learners' attitudes towards learning Mathematics and their overall emotional experiences during the learning process. By analyzing this influence, the study aimed to provide insights into the potential

benefits of using games in Mathematics education for promoting positive affective outcomes among learners. The study finds that game-based learning has positive effects on learners' motivation, engagement, attitudes, enjoyment, state of flow, etc. Current theories of education place significant emphasis on the development of learners' affective domain, which is linked to the subject and its instruction. However, game-based learning is sometimes not working for all types of learners. Karakoç et al. (2020) examine the impact of game-based learning methods on learners' academic achievement by means of a meta-analysis. In addition to revealing the overall effect of game-based learning on academic achievement, subgroup analyses were also conducted. The results of the study suggest that the effects of game-based learning on learner achievement are numerous and varied. Furthermore, because of the analyses, it was revealed that the effect of game-based learning on the academic achievement of learners does not differ according to the sub-dimensions of the levels of schooling, the different types of reporting and various disciplines.

Table 6

Summative Test Performance of the Learners in Solving Linear Inequality in One Variable Before and After the Utilization of MATHO as a Localized Teaching Strategy (per Learners' Category)

Level of Performance	First Summative Test Before Utilization of MATHO		Second Summative Test After Utilization of MATHO		Gain Score
	Mean Percentage Score	Descriptive Interpretation	Mean Percentage Score	Descriptive Interpretation	
Outstanding	34.66	Nearly Mastered	67.79	Highly Mastered	33.13
Very Satisfactory	39.62	Nearly Mastered	64.76	Highly Mastered	25.14
Satisfactory	37.89	Nearly Mastered	69.75	Highly Mastered	31.86
Fairly Satisfactory	37.76	Nearly Mastered	52.33	Mastered	14.57
				Mean Gain	26.18
Legend:	75.0049 %	–	100 %	-	Highly Mastered
	50.0049 %	–	75 %	-	Mastered
	25.0049 %	–	50 %	-	Nearly Mastered
	0 %	–	25 %	-	Least Mastered

Table 6 provide valuable insights into the progress made by the learners at different levels in Solving Linear Inequality in One Variable. It is intriguing to note that outstanding learners achieved the highest gain, with an impressive score of 33.13. Following closely behind are the satisfactory learners, who attained a commendable gain score of 31.86. Meanwhile, the very satisfactory learners showcased a respectable improvement with a gain score of 25.14. Lastly, the fairly satisfactory learners exhibited a positive advancement with a gain score of 14.57. Notably, the satisfactory learners consistently maintained their positions across various least learned competencies, showcasing their commitment to continuous growth and development. This highlights the potential of utilizing MATHO in nurturing and satisfying learners at different levels, enabling them to enhance their critical thinking and problem-solving skills in Mathematics and achieve their educational goals.

It is related to the study of Alcantara and Bacsa (2017). focused on evaluating the critical thinking and problem-solving skills of grade 7 public secondary learners in Mathematics. It involved assessing learners' abilities to think critically and solve Mathematical problems effectively within this specific grade level. The study likely investigated various factors influencing these skills, such as teaching methods, curriculum design, and learner demographics. By analyzing the critical thinking and problem-solving skills of grade 7 learners, the study aimed to provide insights into their Mathematical proficiency and identify potential areas for improvement in Mathematics education at the secondary level.

Part II. The Gain Score of Groups of Learners After Exposing to MATHO as a Localized Teaching Strategy

Table 7

The Potential of MATHO to Enhance Mathematical Skills of Grade 7 Learners Based on the Overall Gain Score of Different Levels of Learners in the Three Least Learned Competencies

Least Learned Competencies	Average Gain Score	Overall Gain Score
1. Evaluating Algebraic Expression	41.69	
2. Solving Linear Equation in One Variable	34.39	34.09
3. Solving Linear Inequality in One Variable	26.18	

Table 7 highlights the gains made by the learners at different levels in these three competencies. One of the competencies that saw the highest improvement was

Evaluating Algebraic Expressions, indicating a strong grasp of this fundamental concept. Following closely behind is Solving Linear Equations in One Variable, which requires a deep understanding of Mathematical principles. Finally, Solving Linear Inequalities in One Variable proved to be a challenging but crucial skill for learners to master. Despite the complexity of the three competencies, it is evident that utilizing MATHO in all three competencies have had a positive impact in the performance of the learners in Mathematics. However, it is important to note that the effectiveness of game-based learning can vary depending on the complexity of the lesson and the specific learning goals. Educators should carefully consider the learning objectives and choose the most suitable instructional methods for each lesson.

Adipat et al (2021), game-based learning may not always be applicable to complicated lessons. One study mentioned in the search results found that digital games were compared to other instruction conditions without games, and the results showed that digital games and simulations had a significant positive effect on students' cognitive competencies.

Part III. Potential of MATHO as a Localized Teaching Strategy to Enhance the Mathematical Skills of Grade 7 Learners of Gumaca National High School

The analysis of the data revealed that learners who consistently engaged with the MATHO showed remarkable improvement. This only suggested that MATHO has the potential to not only enhance mathematical skills but also developed critical thinking and analytical reasoning. The findings also indicate that the localized teaching strategy plays a crucial role in supporting learners' success. By tailoring the content to the specific needs and challenges, MATHO ensures that learners have access to relevant and relative examples. This localized teaching approach fosters a deeper understanding of Mathematical concepts and promotes greater engagement among learners. Additionally, the study found that MATHO's interactive features, such as quizzes and games, effectively engage learners and make the learning process enjoyable. This aspect is important as it helps maintain learners' motivation and enthusiasm towards Mathematics. Overall, these results demonstrated the effectiveness of the MATHO in improving Mathematical skills and highlight its potential to transform education by providing accessible and engaging learning materials for learners worldwide.

According to Creus (2019), using locally relevant instructional materials led to high learner performance, the importance of the lessons for the learners' day-to-day lives, easily understood lesson content and activities, enhanced skills, and creativity, and, as an innovation, the ability to meet learners' learning needs while also potentially advancing their careers. Coherence to the study of Heid and Gestwicki (2016), the effects of manipulative use on the achievement of Mathematics of high- and low-achieving learners are investigated. According to the authors, the use of manipulatives helped both groups of learners understand Mathematical concepts, although the advantage was greatest for high achievers. According to the study, manipulatives can aid high achievers in connecting disparate ideas and deepening their comprehension of Mathematical

subjects. The study also underlines how crucial it is to give learners manipulatives that are appropriate for their age and skill level.

Part IV. The Proposed Implementing Rules and Guidelines in Utilizing MATHO as a Localized Teaching Strategy to Enhance the Mathematical Skills of Grade 7 Learners

Based on the analysis of the MATHO as a localized teaching strategy for improving the Mathematical skills of grade 7 learners of Gumaca National High School, Gumaca West District, Division of Quezon, the implementing rules, and guidelines in utilization of MATHO as a localized teaching strategy was proposed. This aims to facilitate the utilization of MATHO to improve learners' Mathematical skills. The implementing rules and guidelines emphasize the consistent interaction with the MATHO, fostering the development of problem-solving skills and a deeper understanding of Mathematics. This not only yields academic benefits but also imparts valuable skills for future endeavors. MATHO's potential lies in its capacity to make the learning of Mathematics enjoyable and interactive, fostering a positive attitude towards the subject. By incorporating MATHO, learners can overcome apprehensions about Mathematics, ultimately building confidence in tackling complex problems. The implementing rules and guidelines serve the purpose of sharing and maximizing the potential of MATHO as an effective tool for enhancing Mathematical skills among grade 7 learners.

Making the rules and guidelines, the researcher used the format released by regional office, Curriculum and Learning Management Division and Learning Resources (CLMD) and Learning Resources Management and Development System (LRMDS). This format serves as a basis for the development of contextualized learning resources to all public schools.

The proposed implementing rules and guidelines in utilizing MATHO as a localized teaching strategy contains the following: (1) Materials Needed. This section outlines the materials required to conduct the MATHO game. This may include game cards, markers, score sheets, and any other specific items essential for the game. Ensuring that all necessary materials are readily available contributes to the smooth execution of the activity; (2) Preparation for Game. The instructions are provided on how to prepare the MATHO game. This may involve setting up the game area, distributing materials to participants, and explaining the rules and objectives. Adequate preparation ensures that the game runs efficiently and that participants understand their roles and responsibilities; (3) Mechanics of the Game. This section details the rules and mechanics governing how MATHO is played. It may include information on how to start and end the game, the order of turns, scoring procedures, and any special rules or conditions. Clear and concise instructions help participants engage with the game effectively and understand the dynamics of gameplay; (4) Sample Questions. Sample questions are included to illustrate the type of Mathematical questions that the participants will encounter during the game. These questions align with the educational objectives and are designed to challenge

participants' problem-solving skills. Sample questions provide clarity on the level of difficulty and content covered, ensuring that the game is both educational and enjoyable.

These components in the proposed implementing rules and guidelines, organizers and participants gain a comprehensive understanding of how to conduct and participate in the MATHO game. Clarity in material requirements, preparation, procedure, game mechanics, and sample questions contributes to a positive and effective learning experience for the grade 7 learners of Gumaca National High School, Gumaca West District, Division of Quezon.

DISCUSSION

Summary

This study focused on the potential of MATHO as a localized teaching strategy in enhancing the mathematical skills of grade 7 learners of Gumaca National High School, Gumaca West District, Division of Quezon. The researcher conducted a regular basis class and identified the struggling learners in Mathematics during the teaching and learning process and through the summative test. The researcher conducted a summative test and learners who will get 75% lowest score on the said test will undergo in the remediation class and the researcher will utilize the MATHO as a localized teaching strategy.

Specifically, this research sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the performance of the group of learners in the summative test before and after the utilization of MATHO as a localized teaching strategy in the following least mastered competencies:
 - 1.1 Evaluating Algebraic Expression;
 - 1.2 Solving Linear Equation in One Variable; and
 - 1.3 Solving Linear Inequality in One Variable?
2. What is the gain score of the learners after exposing to MATHO as a localized teaching strategy?
3. Is MATHO, as a localized teaching strategy, has the potential to enhance the Mathematical skills of grade 7 learners of Gumaca National High School?
4. Based on the results of the findings, what implementing rules, and guidelines in utilizing MATHO could be proposed by the researcher?

This study applied the quantitative experimental method of research dealing with the study of remediation class of below average performer learners in Mathematics.

The researcher used a 30-item validated and analyzed researcher-made test to administer the first summative and second summative test before and after the utilization of MATHO as a localized teaching strategy.

Summary of Findings

Based on the results, the major findings of the study were:

1. The result of the performance of learners in the summative test before and after the utilization of MATHO as a localized teaching strategy in the following least mastered competencies:

1.1. In Evaluating Algebraic Expression, the outstanding learners demonstrated the highest level of improvement, closely followed by the very satisfactory learners. The satisfactory learners ranked third in terms of progress, while the fairly satisfactory learners showed some improvement as well.

1.2. Solving Linear Equations in One Variable, all levels of learners obtained an average score on the first summative test. However, after utilizing MATHO as a localized teaching strategy and taking the second summative test, it was observed that the group of very satisfactory learners attained the highest score with a gain score of 36.92. This was closely followed by the fairly satisfactory learners who achieved a gain score of 34.62. Meanwhile, satisfactory learners received a gain score of 33.29.

1.3. Solving Linear Inequality in One Variable, the outstanding learners achieved the highest gain, with an impressive score of 33.13. Following closely behind are the satisfactory learners, who attained a commendable gain score of 31.86. Meanwhile, the very satisfactory learners showcased a respectable improvement with a gain score of 25.14. Lastly, the fairly satisfactory learners exhibited a positive advancement with a gain score of 14.57.

2. The gain score of groups of learners after exposing to MATHO as a localized teaching strategy

One of the competencies that saw the highest improvement was Evaluating Algebraic Expressions. Following closely behind is Solving Linear Equations in One Variable, which requires a deep understanding of mathematical principles. Finally, Solving Linear Inequalities in One Variable proved to be a challenging but crucial skill for students to master.

3. Potential of MATHO, as a localized teaching strategy, to enhance the mathematical skills of grade 7 learners of Gumaca National High School

The analysis of the data revealed that learners who consistently engaged with MATHO showed significant improvement. This suggests that MATHO has potential in enhancing the Mathematical skills of grade 7 learners.

4. The Proposed Implementing Rules and Guidelines in the Utilization of MATHO

Based on the results of analysis of the Potential of MATHO as a Localized Teaching Strategy in Enhancing The Mathematical Skills of Grade 7 Learners of Gumaca National High School, Gumaca West District, Division of Quezon, the implementing rules and guidelines in utilizing MATHO is hereby proposed by the researcher.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

The MATHO as a localized teaching strategy has its potential in enhancing and honing the Mathematical skills of grade 7 learners of Gumaca National High School, Gumaca West District, Division of Quezon. Its characteristics in engaging learners to drive significant improvement are remarkable. The analysis of the data further highlighted the potential of MATHO as a localized teaching strategy in realizing learners' understanding of mathematical concepts. By consistently engaging with MATHO, learners can develop their problem-solving skills and deepen their knowledge in Mathematics. This not only benefits them academically but also equips them with valuable skills for future success. The potential of MATHO lies in its ability to make learning Mathematics enjoyable and interactive, fostering a positive attitude towards the subject. With MATHO, learners can overcome their fear of math and gain confidence in tackling complex problems. The positive impact that MATHO has on learners is a testament to its potential as an effective localized teaching strategy, and an innovation that can be used in the teaching learning process in the field of Mathematics Education.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations were forwarded:

1. Based on the results of the first and second summative tests, it is recommended to all Mathematics Teachers that MATHO may be utilized as a localized teaching strategy in some topics in Mathematics. The material proved that all levels of performance of learners has significantly improved, especially in satisfactory learners.
2. Based on the analysis of the learner's performance utilizing MATHO in different learning competencies, it is evident that there are significant differences in their outcomes. To all administrators, may provide a support, in utilizing localized materials effectively to address these differences and enhance learner achievement. Working

together may elevate the quality in learning Mathematics and ensure that every learner can thrive in this subject.

3. Considering that MATHO has potential, the school heads and teachers may collaborate to encourage Mathematics teachers to utilize MATHO as a localized teaching strategy to help learners who need assistance in improving their Mathematics skills in the classroom. Future researchers may replicate the study to re-evaluate the potential of MATHO as a localized teaching strategy or introduce other teaching strategies to enhance the Mathematical skills of the learners.

4. The researcher wholeheartedly advocates for future researchers to delve into their own inquiries regarding the potential of MATHO or to validate its utility as localized teaching strategy. It is essential to encourage further investigation, analysis, and experimentation to comprehensively assess the capabilities and impact of this educational tool.

By endorsing future research endeavors, the aim is to expand the body of knowledge surrounding MATHO and its potential contributions in enhancing learning outcomes. This call for continued exploration recognizes the dynamic nature of educational interventions and the need for ongoing refinement and adaptation to meet the evolving needs of learners.

In this discernment, future researchers are encouraged to embark on rigorous studies, employing diverse methodologies, and involving varied learner populations to gain a more comprehensive understanding of how MATHO can be optimized for educational success. These efforts will not only enrich the existing literature but also offer valuable insights that can inform educational practices and contribute to the ongoing improvement of Mathematics Education.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

After obtaining approval from the school head at Gumaca National High School (GNHS) and endorsement from the School Division Superintendent (SDS) through approval letters signed by the Dean of Graduate Studies of Marinduque State College (MSC), the authors proceeded with their research in strict adherence to ethical standards. Before initiating data collection, the authors ensured that informed consent was obtained from all participants, confirming their voluntary participation in attending classes during the utilization of the MATHO, a localized teaching strategy. Participants were assured of their right to withdraw from the study at any stage without facing any consequences. Stringent measures were implemented to safeguard the anonymity of respondents, preserving the confidentiality of their identities throughout the research process. The authors maintained a steadfast commitment to prioritizing the well-being of all participants involved in the study. They affirm that no conflicts of interest existed during the research process, and plagiarism was rigorously avoided to uphold academic integrity. Furthermore, the interpretation of findings was approached with impartiality to minimize bias, ensuring the reliability and validity of the study outcomes. The results obtained were utilized exclusively for research purposes, reflecting the authors' dedication to ethical

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